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AI and African Literary Studies

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Introduction

AI technology is often described with language relating to the entire spectrum of colonial discourse: on the one hand, AI is cannibalistic, representing the worst version of the imperial monstrous, and on the other, it is extractive, following the same economic blueprint of the scramble for Africa. Both formulations pick up on very real concerns about AI, concerns that, as this paper will argue, we need to take seriously in the field of African literature because our field is particularly vulnerable to the biases of literary data created in and for the global north. But the problem with these formulations, is that they also play into a general suspicion in the humanities about AI technology, which may potentially result in a lack of much needed engagement with actively changing the preconditions from which AI operates today. This paper attempts to disentangle both the problems and potentials of AI technology as they pertain to the field of African literary studies. It does so highly mindful of the simultaneity of the decolonization movement and the rise of access to AI technology through Generative Pre-Trained Transformers (GPTs) in the mid-2010s. Calls, over the last decade, to decolonise literary studies have reached an impasse in terms of the continued dominance of the English language in the field, as well as its heavy reliance on commercially produced literature from the global north. The commercial and linguistic bias of the literary data being used to train Large Language Models (LLMs) redoubles the problem of decolonisation in a time of AI. Yet, as this paper argues, the field of African literary studies can also harness the power of AI tools to ensure that the African literary data available for LLM training is diverse, Africa-based, and not only determined by commercial factors.

The simultaneity of AI and the decolonizing movement has instantiated a significant body of scholarly work. In “Can Artificial Intelligence Be Decolonized?”, Rachel Adams notes that this matter has been addressed, first and foremost, through discussions about the ethical standards governing AI, given that what GPTs generate is riddled with the biases of the data it is trained on, and this data is notoriously homogenous in terms of the geographical location it is produced (mostly the global north) and the ideologies it represents. Whilst acknowledging the need for ethical guidelines that can avoid such biases, Adams notes the contradiction of such standards being “paternalistically positioned as universal,” while in reality these benchmarks are entirely fashioned in the academies of the global north (Adams 184; 182-3). Nowhere was this fact more excruciatingly obvious than in the article, “The Global Landscape of AI Ethics Guidelines,” published in the *Nature*-branded journal, *Nature Machine Intelligence* in 2019. As Adams points out, among the “84 AI ethics standards” enumerated in that article, “none listed are from the African continent or even the Global South” (Adams 183). The work of decolonization in AI is, it would appear, a long way off. Addressing this matter through a set of practical guidelines, Shakir Mohamed, Marie-

Therese Png and William Isaac's "Decolonial AI: Sociotechnical Foresight in Artificial Intelligence" diagnoses three core challenges in the work of decolonising AI: "algorithmic coloniality" or "algorithmic oppression" (Adams 183); the exploitative practices involved when "large volumes of data [need to be] annotated by human experts" (Mohamed, Png, and Isaac 668) or in beta-testing¹ in national contexts with low-bars on the regulation of data; and the dominance of economically developed nations in producing global policy on AI governance (Mohamed, Png, and Isaac 670).

But what does this mean for the field of literary studies? How does algorithmic coloniality infiltrate the literary classroom, or what do the "ghost workers" (Gray and Suri, cited in Mohamed, Png, and Isaac 668) of big tech and data have to do with literary methods? The field of African literature has not yet addressed this issue,² despite the fact that African literary studies are particularly vulnerable to negative impact by AI technology. This is because of a combination of historical factors, most pertinently that colonial ontologies in library and archival science prioritized written works in European languages as the material of the literary; that Africa's written production in the late 19th and early 20th century that was primarily located in ephemeral venues such as newspapers and pamphlets; and that structural adjustment has such devastating effects on local publishing on the continent.³ The scale at which the colonial legacies of knowledge production and information science influence AI, as well as technical complexity through which AI operates, makes this matter seem one beyond the disciplinary scope of literary studies. Yet, without the view from the domain of specialisation, the threats to that field of specialisation by such technological advances will not be adequately addressed and averted.

¹ Beta-testing is "testing and fine-tuning of early versions of software systems to help identify issues in their usage in settings with real users and use cases" (Mohamed, Png and Isaac 668.)

² Shōla Adenekan's 2021 book *African Literature in the Digital Age* and Akin Adesokan's *Everything is Sampled* (2023) both address digital technologies and African literature, but from the perspective of how these technologies are integrated into creative processes, rather than what they mean for the future of the African literary archive. Neither of these books discuss AI and its relevance for the scholarly field. *Postcolonial text* published a special edition on 'Digital Africas' (15, 3-4, 2020), in which all the contributions are similarly focused on digital publishing and platform distribution (Arenberg), new media (Ndakalako-Bannikov), Literary networks (Krishnan and Wallis, Diegner) digital obsolescence (Stern), and digital spaces and literary forms (Cobham-Sander, Sacks, Opoku-Agyemang, Shringarpure, Ligaga), but none discuss the matter of AI. James Yékú's "Digital African Literatures and the Coloniality of Data" in *The Cambridge Journal of Postcolonial Literary Inquiry* takes up the matter of data politics and the politics of proprietary platforms, but does not discuss LLMs or AI excepting in passing to comment on LLM's inadequate African language knowledge (a matter I will return to below). The only article to include a brief discussion of LLMs in *Journal of African Literature Association* is Chris Thurman's 'African-language Shakespeares: Reflections on Archival and Creative Practice in the Digital Sphere', but it is only mentioned in passing. *Research in African Literature* included an early paper by Anne-Marie Dauphin-Tinturier on 'Publishing and Hypermedia', that touched on artificial intelligence, but recent issues of the journal do not offer a sustained engagement with this matter.

³ See Sarah Brouillette, *UNESCO and the Fate of the Literary*, (Stanford University Press, 2019).

A tightening circle: hypervisibility and AI

There is a further factor that should be addressed in the field of African literature, one which has to do with current practices in teaching and research that have the potential to feed LLMs with increasingly narrower data on the field. This is the continued dominance of the method of close reading in the field, despite the fact that close reading has been substantially critiqued by African literary scholars for its ‘extractionist’ tendencies (Harris and Hållén 4), its ornamentalization of Africanness (Julien 672), and the imaginative, political, psychological and social gap that must – yet cannot ever fully – be traversed for readers to interpret texts from contexts that they are foreign to (Quayson 2003). My concern here is more fundamental and takes a simple observation by Franco Moretti as a springboard. In ‘Conjectures on World Literatures’, Moretti wrote that

[t]he trouble with close reading (in all of its incarnations, from the new criticism to deconstruction) is that it necessarily depends on an extremely small canon. This may have become an unconscious and invisible premise by now, but it is an iron one nonetheless: you invest so much in individual texts only if you think that very few of them really matter. (Moretti 57)

Nowhere has this proved to be more axiomatic than in the field of African literature, which is a field deeply biased towards US and European published books – primarily novels and short story collections – in English by African émigré writers. This is not to say that there is not a rich and productive body of scholarship paying attention to African-language literary forms published or circulating on the continent itself, in a myriad of African languages. Nor is it a critique of African literary studies journals, all of which could be shown to actively resist the over-production of a small canon for the field. Rather, the problem only becomes apparent when we view publishing tendencies on African literary materials at scale, across all indexed academic journals.

To get such a measure of the amount of work produced on, for example, a specific writer or text is complicated by the fact that metadata is captured differently and unevenly in different academic repositories. For this reason, instead of searching for a universal number of publications via a search platform like Google scholar, or through an AI with access to a range of data repositories, I decided to run a sample test on four major African authors (Ngũgĩ wa Thiong’o, Chinua Achebe, J. M. Coetzee, and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie)⁴ on one

⁴ The choice of these authors was determined from the results of Lily Saint and Bhakti Shringarpure’s blog post “African Literature is a country” (<https://africasacountry.com/2020/08/african-literature-is-a-country>). In a questionnaire about African literature curricula answered by 105 teachers of the subject, largely based in US or European universities, Saint and Shringarpure found that “Ngũgĩ wa Thiong’o is the most taught writer (87 mentions). Nigerians, Chinua Achebe and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, are similarly popular on syllabi (82 mentions each) while J.M. Coetzee is the next most taught author (59 mentions)”. While Saint and Shringarpure’s data set is not large enough to warrant a full comparative study between texts taught on

single academic repository, the MLA International Bibliography. To exclude results on materials written by the authors themselves, I entered the author names into the subject field of the search. I also included two further major writers, who worked respectively in Kiswahili (Shaaban bin Robert) and isiZulu (Mazisi Kunene). The results illustrate how many scholarly and peer-reviewed publications are included in the MLA International Bibliography, according to type of publication (journal article, book chapter, books, and dissertations) on the works of these authors (see Figure 1).

Figure 1.

	Chinua Achebe	J. M. Coetzee	Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o	Chimamanda Adichie	Shaaban bin Robert	Mazisi Kunene
Journal Articles	2850	2610	1550	850	75	55
Book Chapters	1300	1370	750	350	20	15
Books	150	430	150	90	8	4
Dissertations	750	440	350	10*	25	18
Total	5050	4850	2800	1300	128	92

Table 1: Detailed data for Figure 1.⁵

Over and above the obvious and oft-stated fact of the dominance of the English-language (or, in Ngũgĩ’s case, widely circulated English-translated materials) over writing in African-

university curricula and works published in global English academia, it is safe to say that the same writers and books are likely to dominate both fields.

⁵ All values above 100 are rounded up or down to the nearest decimal point, while all values below 100 are exact.

language writing, what remains striking is the magnitude of that disparity. That there are approximately 430 monographs on the works of J. M. Coetzee must be indicative of an overproduction when compared to the four monographs on the work of his compatriot, Mazisi Kunene. What is important to keep in mind, though, is that while the MLA International Bibliography gives us one optic on ‘international’ knowledge production, no data repository ever represents the entire picture of knowledge production on any given topic. Rather, a data repository is indicative only of the limits of the data it includes. One clear indication of this is the disparity between the ten dissertations included in this dataset on the works of Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie and the 92 dissertations with Adichie’s work stated as their ‘topic’ in ProQuest’s Dissertations and Theses Global database. The disparity can be explained by the fact that the MLA International Bibliography only includes “dissertations available through stable repositories” and does not include “unpublished dissertations,” (MLA International Bibliography ‘Content’) whereas the ProQuest database draws from much more expansive content.

Such discrepancies in data are all-the-more apparent when one looks at (or for) African-based and African-published knowledge production. To illustrate this, we can take a closer look at the constitution and provenance of data in ProQuest’s Dissertation and Theses Global data repository. Using Clarivate’s Web of Science search tool to explore this dataset, I searched for all dissertations and theses on the topic of ‘African Literature’. This yielded 7 295 works in ProQuest, of which 5 613 (or 76%) are from universities in the United States. Only 815 of these dissertations are from African universities, with a major bias towards South African Universities (accounting for 758 dissertations), while Nigeria (41), Tanzania (13) and Egypt (3) are the only other African contexts mentioned. The top 5 sources constitute 97% of the total countries represented in this list.

Country	ProQuest listed dissertations on ‘African Literature’ – Count
United States	5 613
South Africa	758
Canada	465
England	164
Portugal	72

Table 2. Count of dissertations or theses with ‘African Literature’ as their topic in ProQuest data

A similar issue is true of African journals, and especially African-language journals, which, like many African university dissertation repositories, have been largely left out of so-called ‘global’ databases due to fact that they have not been indexed by these databases. One reason for this is that many African journals remain print-based without the digital resources required to run their ventures online, but a more problematic reason is a bias in the quality markers applied by data repositories towards journals based in the global north.

The politics of journal indexing repeats the politics of knowledge that have obstinately excluded African-produced knowledge from global flows, whilst simultaneously using Africa as a site of “raw fact: of the minutiae from which Euromodernity might fashion its testable theories and transcendent truths. Just as it has long capitalized on non-Western ‘raw materials’ by ostensibly adding value and refinement to them” (Comaroff and Comaroff 114). To put it very simply, without indexation, these journals lack global visibility, searchability, and impact.

To return to the topic of AI, when it comes to the primary materials of African literature, the hypervisibility of scholarly work on authors like Coetzee, Adichie, and other globally renowned writers, means that these works are more likely to be more accessible as materials that LLMs use for training than knowledge produced in Africa. Consequently, and worryingly, the fact that AI’s will be increasingly trained on a skewed version of the field will exacerbate this hypervisibility even further as GPTs fail to capture a more varied and diverse set of data. While discussions about GPTs are often stuck at the level of literary teachers’ concerns about the extent to which their students use the technology to cheat the essay-writing system, the issue of what materials are used to train GPTs and the relevance of that for our field, is a far larger concern.

Recently, a major lawsuit was brought by the author Sarah Silverman and others against Open AI’s ChatGPT and Meta’s LLaMA, after evidence that these GPTs used data that (in LLaMa’s case) came from a database (Bibliotik) that harvested data from public domain sites such as Project Gutenberg, but also from the Book3 dataset, which included pirated books from shadow libraries (Masood). In light of this lawsuit, tech companies are reticent to openly share information about the materials they are using to train their LLMs.⁶ We can speculate, however, that creative work that is not in the public domain is unlikely to form the major substance of this training (unless publishers of creative works begin to make deals with big tech like their academic counterparts are doing – of which, more below). This is why, as teachers know, GPTs are bad at close reading. If the work that a GPT is ‘reading’ is not available as data, it can only extract textual data as evidence from secondary works that are available to it. The cheapest and easiest and legally least complicated literary material used to train LLMs is that produced on social media or sites like Goodreads or other ‘literary review’ pages. This explains why student literary essays that rely heavily on GPTs often read like bland and flat descriptions of a plot or theme, and why quotes from texts are sometimes slightly incorrect (pages and editions are certainly beyond the capacity of most GPTs at this point) or even fully hallucinated in some instances. In these cases, the GPT is not using the original text as data, but is extracting that data second-hand, through human readers who introduce errors, for example, into the transcription of quotes, who have used

⁶ For a full discussion of this matter, see Masood.

different editions of any given text, and who possibly assert unevidenced claims about the texts in question.⁷

For African literature, the fact that publishers of creative works have largely not been open to selling their content for LLM development could be considered a good thing: since most African published writing emerges after the mid 20th century, almost all African published works are not yet in the public domain. As such, student misuse of GPTs when discussing African literary materials are going to continue to be relatively easy to spot for the time being. On the other hand, the materials that are being used as training materials for LLMs are heavily loaded towards historical European texts in the public domain or English-language online secondary materials of low academic quality.

It is difficult to assess the real impact of digital hypervisibility of certain kinds of materials for students, but we might speculate that there must be at least some correlation (and an ironic one at that) between the trending of Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's TED talk on the 'Danger of the Single Story' (currently sitting at 14,8 million views) and the amount of academic publication written on her work since that YouTube distributed talk went viral (a current number of academic works with the prompt Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie as a subject on Google Scholar is 3 040).⁸ The danger we face with the almost wholesale integration of GPTs modelled on materials with a low-bar for copyright into our scholarly fields is the exacerbation of such algorithmic trending.

We are facing two interrelated problems here: first, the questionable quality of easily usable content for training GPTs and secondly, the hypervisibility of certain data, authorised by databases that have a distinct US and European bias. To address the problem of poor academic quality in GPT results, big tech has made multimillion dollar deals with academic publishers to use their content as training materials for LLMs.⁹ While some publishers, like Cambridge University Press, are exploring an opt-in agreement for their authors, other major academic publishers, like Wiley and Taylor and Francis, have already sold content for the purposes of LLM training.¹⁰ Because LLMs require a lot of content for training, it is no surprise that these deals are made with large parent companies of academic publishers such as Informa (parent company to Taylor and Francis). Smaller presses, which would include

⁷ The accessibility of fandoms for LLM training could easily introduce information about any given character in a text that did not actually occur in the text itself, but in a fandom on the novel in question.

⁸ It is important to remember that Google Scholar includes materials that have not been peer reviewed, such as pre-prints.

⁹ See Masood and Kwon and Schonfeld for three accounts of these deals.

¹⁰ Diana Kwon reports in *Nature*, that "In May [2024], Informa, the parent company of the UK academic publisher Taylor & Francis, announced that it made a US\$10-million deal to license content to Microsoft. The next month, the US academic publisher Wiley announced to its investors that it had earned \$23 million from a deal with an unnamed firm developing generative-AI models. In September, the company said that it expected to earn another \$21 million from such agreements this financial year".

most of the university and journal presses on the African continent, do not have the volume of content that these models need for effective training. The result is the redoubling of a skewed politics of knowledge production away from the global south, a problem that intensifies existing algorithmic inequality: here the very model of ‘thinking’ about the field of the literary is generated by materials heavily dominated by the English language and by academics writing from and for the global north.

Tactics for decolonising AI for African Literary Studies

It is instructive for us in the field of African literature to learn from the groundwork done by African studies scholars working in related fields¹¹ and in scholarship that takes up larger concerns of AI’s colonial heritage for postcolonial and African contexts, such as the problems of the extractive aspects of data, the data-divide, and the colonial imprint in the digital archive.¹² Shakir Mohamed, Marie-Therese Png and William Isaac offer “three tactics for future AI design” (672) which can be productively applied to the field of African Literary Studies. They describe these tactics as “supporting a critical technical practice of AI, establishing reciprocal engagements and reverse pedagogies and the renewal of affective and political community” (Mohamed, Png and Isaac, 672). By Critical Technical Practice of AI (CTP), the authors refer to finding “a middle ground between the technical work of developing new AI algorithms and the reflexive work of criticism that uncovers hidden assumptions and alternative ways of working” (672). Some of the features of this tactic that will be of particular importance in the discussion to follow are algorithmic fairness and equality, data diversity, and engaging “technologies of resistance” (Mohamed, Png and Isaac 674). The second tactic, “Reciprocal Engagements and Reverse Tutelage” (674) involves an inversion of the line of paternalistic knowledge production from metropole to periphery, which also involves a need for new technical design, community engaged research, and fluid or open technologies to allow for continued dialogue with communities and other stakeholders. The third tactic is to create “renewed affective and political communities” (676), which I elaborate as a mode of collaboration in knowledge creation that literary scholars, stuck as we are in the model of single-author publication, are far from achieving.

In applying these tactics to the field of African literary studies, I found that they overlap with one another in ways that made them impossible to entirely disentangle. In what follows, then, I offer reflections on various aspects of the roadmap that Mohamed, Png and Isaac offer, even as I do not adhere to it strictly.

At its most simple, Critical Technical Practice is a process of bringing critical thinking into the processes of technical development, in this case for the purpose of algorithmic fairness and

¹¹ Frédéric Madore’s explorations into AI workflows for archival processing, analysis and retrieval, are of particular relevance to this paper (see Madore).

¹² See Couldry and Mejias, Arakpogun, and Thakur, respectively.

data equality and ethics. One of the core problems noted above is the fact that global data is particularly lacking when it comes to African produced data (for example, data on African languages for improved translation quality between, to and from, African languages, and in our case, data on materials not catalogued or indexed in the world's most powerful data repositories.) For data diversity, we need more substantial indexing of African-based journals and dissertations/theses. This is what the African Journal Initiative, a collaboration between African Books Collective and Pluto Journals, is addressing by indexing 6 African-based academic journals per year, (African Books Collective, "African Journals Initiative") a pace that indicates the scale of resources required for this work. It is precisely this need for extensive human labour in annotation and metadata creation that can, as Mohamed, Png and Isaac point out, introduce exploitative labour to the problem of making data fairer and more diverse.

How can we tip the scales of a massive under-representation of literary data without becoming complicit in such exploitative processes? Across the continent, librarians are already working with digitization teams to preserve unique materials on the digital repositories housed at their libraries, but library resources are stretched, and the amount of data transcription required to correct the imbalance is too large to expect librarians to shoulder the weight of this correction alone. To illustrate the scale of this problem, I refer to a dataset I have recently published by the African Literary Metadata project on the authors and literary content in the literary magazine *Staffrider* (Harris "Literary Content") a South African literary magazine which had a run of 37 issues between 1978 and 1993. The full dataset includes 713 individual authors and 1772 individual works, but in standard cataloguing practice (for obvious reasons of availability of resources) all that was captured in the online metadata of this body of work is the date of publication, volume and issue number of the 37 issues of the magazines. The problem for African literary studies is the significance that literary and small magazines played in African literature in the mid- to late-20th century. To get a sense of the extent to which data about contributors to such magazines are absent from global data, I reconciled the 713 individual authors in this dataset against existing data in Wikidata and in the VIAF authority file, since these two datasets together provide significant coverage of formal (VIAF) and informal (Wikidata) linked data available globally.¹³ Of these 713 authors, only 146 are found to have existing data in these datasets. Given the fact that South African authors are significantly better represented in global databases than authors from most other African countries,¹⁴ this

¹³ VIAF (Virtual International Authority File) collates library data on authors and works (irrespective of spelling, language, or variation) under a single unique identity number. Almost all formally published authors can be found in VIAF since it is connected to the databases of numerous national libraries, including the Library of Congress, as well as to Wikidata, which enables a broader range of author data.

¹⁴ Of 8951 African literary authors identified on Wikidata, 1586 are South African, amounting to 17,7% of the total. Egypt comes in at a close second with 1456 authors, and Nigeria with 1257, after which there is a sharp cut off in available author data per country. This means that these three countries represent, in total, 48% of all wikidata on African authors. Furthermore, only 4308 of these wikidata author records link to VIAF author data, a major database of all authors whose works are catalogued in 56 national library databases from across

number must be understood as a good return on existing African literary data – even though the match percentage is only just over 20%. The remaining 80% – amounting to 567 authors – are uncatalogued in any global database.

In the case of *Staffrider*, the freely accessible digital copies¹⁵ of the magazines made the transcription of the data possible and the publication of that data under a Creative Commons License means that it will become free for use by, amongst other parties, companies or initiatives using it for training LLMs. In short, the 567 previously uncatalogued authors will become visible in GPT generated material. But the transcription work for a data set of this size is extremely demanding, requiring not just careful copying of data from the digital copies of the texts, but also time-consuming editing to clean and harmonise the data (for example in determining a standard for varied spellings of an author's name). Perhaps this is the kind of slow and humble work we simply need to put in if we are to feed global data with greater diversity from the African continent. Indeed, the pace of this work seems itself valuable in the era of AI. In *Slow Metadata*, Rachel Sagner Buurma and Jon Shaw make precisely this point by describing the methods of their Early Novel Database, in which they argue for the importance of slowness and care in the age-old methods of “catalogers, index builders, taxonomists, subject librarians, bibliographers, researchers, [and] literary critics” (Buurma and Shaw 193). Yet, as much as I agree with Sagner Buurma and Shaw about the value of slow transcription, the inequalities between the formal literary global catalogue and the data that remains trapped in analogue form in African print, audio and film, requires us to find alternative ways of capturing such data at greater speed.

Such methods, if applied to African Literary data, enable Mohamed, Png and Isaac's second tactic of reversing the direction of knowledge production, and this reversal can be scaled up significantly with the use of AI technology as has been recently evidenced in Frédéric Madore's groundbreaking work. Madore runs a project called 'Islam West Africa Collection', in which he has developed an AI-powered workflow to increase the sensitivity and accuracy of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) on an array of digitized magazine and newspaper materials.¹⁶ Madore's method uses “an automated OCR process without manual review, enhanced by AI, specifically the GPT-4o model, to correct the OCR output.” This increases the efficiency of OCR by “significantly reduc[ing] document processing time, enabling faster access to a wider range of materials” (Islamic West Africa Collection, “Optical character recognition, OCR”). The method also improves scalability, enabling Madore to “process large collections of documents without the need for extensive human resources, making it possible to maintain and expand the database” (Islamic West Africa Collection, “Optical

the globe. Of those 4308 authors who appear in formal data, 966 are South African. In sum, this means that 22,5% of formalised African literary author data currently on Wikidata is South African. These statistics were compiled by Gijs Aangenendt.

¹⁵ These are available on the Digital Innovation South Africa site at the University of Kwa-Zulu Natal, South Africa (<https://disa.ukzn.ac.za/st>).

¹⁶ See more about the project at Islamic West Africa Collection, <https://islam.zmo.de/s/westafrica/page/home>

character recognition, OCR"). The process also improves adaptability, because the "AI model continuously improves and adapts to different fonts and layouts commonly found in Islamic magazines and newspapers, improving overall accuracy over time" (Islamic West Africa Collection, "Optical character recognition, OCR"). Finally, the process is cost-effective, significantly reducing "operational costs compared to manual review, which requires significant time and labour" (Islamic West Africa Collection, "Optical character recognition, OCR"). This last factor can address the potential problem of exploiting 'ghost' laborers.

While Madore's model is developed to recognise the layout and text of entire articles in newspapers and magazines, its applicability to being able to find the core metadata on anything from literary materials published in newspapers and magazines, to titles of performances in festival catalogues, or theatre programs, is an exciting prospect. To illustrate by way of example, I refer to the scattered archive of the decommissioned National Theatre Organisation (NTO) of Zimbabwe. When the NTO was decommissioned by the Zimbabwean government in the 2000s, its collection was disaggregated into three main parts. The published books (mostly of English plays or secondary texts published in the U.K.) in the collection were given to the youth-training Reps Theatre, where they are kept in moderately good condition and are being slowly (and manually) indexed on site. A second portion of the NTO archive constituted some play manuscripts by Zimbabwean authors as well as the ephemeral print of the collection, such as the NTO annual festival programs. All these materials were given to Daves Guzha, head of Rooftop Productions based at the Theatre in the Park in Harare.¹⁷ The third portion of the NTO collection, however, was abandoned in an open-air, chicken-wire cage, fully exposed to weather, rats and insects, and currently in a state of serious decay. Because the catalogue to the NTO is missing and there is no digital copy of it that we have been able to locate, it is impossible to assess what materials might be decaying in this abandoned portion of the collection. Archives at risk, like this one, are not uncommon in the cultural sector of African contexts that lack resources for maintaining archives over time. Without a catalogue, and with the actual archive dispersed and, in part, destroyed, the work of cultural organisations are at risk of being completely lost.

In this case, however, a collaboration with the Centre of African Studies at Copenhagen university to digitize and catalogue the personal collection of retired Africanist, Preben Kaarsholm, has provided a partial solution. Kaarsholm's collection includes an almost complete set of the newsletters of the NTO from 1987 to 1997, all in excellent condition.¹⁸ These newsletters, alongside the festival programs for the NTO that were digitized at Rooftop Productions in Harare, constitute important sources of metadata on the lost NTO

¹⁷ These materials have been catalogued and digitized as part of a SANORD (Southern African-Nordic Centre) funded project involving Kelvin Chikonzo, Pedzisai Maedza, Nkululeko Sibanda and I in 2023.

¹⁸ PDF copies of the digitized newsletters are available online through the African Studies Centre, Leiden's library.

archive. Having digitized both the newsletters and the festival programs myself, I made a mental note to do the slow work of transcription on these texts when time allowed. But when I discovered the capacity of Google's Gemini Pro 2.5 AI to provide reliable, structured data from OCR, I simply ran the PDFs of the newsletters through a query¹⁹ and quite effortlessly had an accurate dataset of 96 play titles, including date and venue of production, production company, and playwright (if this had been mentioned in the newsletter). I repeated the exercise for the festival programs²⁰ that we had digitized in Harare, which gave a result of 240 plays from 19 festival programs between 1961 and 1987. This entire process took less than 15 minutes, which, compared to the painstaking work of manually transcribing each title and then having to double-check for human error, would have taken many hours of my time. More importantly, the process has restored what must constitute a major part of the entire missing catalogue of the NTO from 1961 to 1997.

Madore has noted the particular value of LLM powered OCR which allows not only text recognition, but also an understanding of the semantic context in which the text appears. He points out that this can be particularly valuable for dealing with low-grade copies of historical newspapers (Madore). If we consider the importance of late 19th to early 20th century newsprint in the then burgeoning field of African literature, we can start to imagine the value that AI powered OCR for discovery and transcription of data on newspaper text might add to global data on early African literatures. There is one major problem with this approach, and that is the proprietorial license on a GPT like Gemini 2.5.²¹ If we are to properly enable these workflows to enter an enriched and Africa-based creation of open data for better global representation, then we need to ensure that the model is available as Open source. This would constitute a form of technical resistance to large corporate control in ways that align with Mohamed, Png and Isaac's roadmap towards decolonizing AI.

The reversal of the flow of knowledge production from the global north to sites underrepresented in global data is not only a matter of technology, though. When it comes to data, this is just as much about the historical ways in which data has been produced, collected and instrumentalised. A pertinent example is given by Rachel Adams when she discusses the problem of the ways in which personal data assemblages have inherited colonial logics. Adams writes that these assemblages are based on a "fixing of the ontology of the colonies and its people by Western knowledges" (Adams 186). While her own critique does not extend to practical ways forward, in what follows I will outline possible paths for

¹⁹ The prompt read: "List all the plays with their playwrights (where possible) directly referred to in these newsletters. Indicate which newsletter the play is found in. Add date and venue of production and name of theatre company if it appears in the newsletter. Use only these newsletters as the basis of your answers." The 'temperature' was turned to 0 to assure a true account of the materials. The results were fully accurate with no errors other than one typographical error from poor print quality in a newsletter.

²⁰ The prompt read: "The attached documents are programs from a theatre festival. Extract and structure all the data on each individual play, including the scriptwriter, venue and dates of performance, awards won, theatre company." The result was returned as a JSON file in 475 seconds.

²¹ I am indebted to Gijs Aangenendt for this insight.

actively reorganising knowledge models and ontologies that continue to form the basis of most contemporary data repositories. Indigenous studies projects have already come some way in this work in information science,²² but this rich body of work on knowledge ontologies has not been engaged fully in the field of African literary and cultural studies.

James Yékú's "Digital African Literatures and the Coloniality of Data" comes closest to taking up the question. He writes that

data cultures, whether prior to computation or enabled by it, are central to the historical evolution of Blackness. Here, the emphasis is on data cultures or the collection and analyses of data before the use of computers became prevalent. The processes of data collection and organization in these analog contexts supported, for instance, the classification of enslaved people, first in slave ships and later at slave auctions. (Yékú 386)

Yékú takes this point further to illustrate how "datafication as ongoing resource extraction in digital ecologies" is a form of data violence which "makes legible the ways in which the organization and classification of information and knowledge have historically supported the operations and enactments of oppressive power" (Yékú 386). Yékú's core concern is to "resist the extraction and control possibilities of big tech and its unabating corporate power to annex the production of cultural forms to the coloniality of data" (Yékú 385) a concern that extends to LLMs even as Yékú is more focused here on platform proprietorship and capitalism (Yékú 393).

Within the domain of African literary studies, we can add to the history of colonial datafication of people a further analysis as to how the idea of the literary emerged in colonial data. In the 19th century, library science consolidated a classification system that drew a fundamental line between oral expressive forms, such as folk tales, epic and praise poetry, proverbs and other common African spoken forms, (relegated to the then emerging fields of anthropology and ethnography) and 'belles lettres', a written tradition firmly connected to the book object. These library standards, made to fit for the European and American form of the book, continue to shape the knowledge models of the literary in both commercial and archival metadata to this day.²³

Rethinking the ontologies of inherited cataloguing systems, and how they have created and upheld the idea of the literary as biased towards European forms is an enormous task that

²² See, for example, the *te reo Māori* ontology at the National Library of New Zealand (<https://natlib.govt.nz/librarians/nga-upoko-tukutuku>) and the First Nations Classification at the University of British Columbia (<https://xwi7xwa.library.ubc.ca/collections/indigenous-knowledge-organization/>)

²³ For a full discussion of this matter see, Harris's "African Literary Metadata and Makerere University's Library".

requires a collective of African scholars, with wide multilingual expertise, to achieve. But the magnitude of the task should not stop us from preparing the ground for such work. While the formalisation of decolonized knowledge ontologies is a future horizon, we can nevertheless contribute at an individual level to fairer and more diverse data on our field by making strategic use of open research repositories, such as Zenodo. Open repositories allow researchers to publish materials from all stages of their research process: from structured data in tabular form, to research notes, draft papers, conference papers and presentations, bibliographies, and many more. Many humanities scholars balk at the idea of making their research data and/or notes publicly available by publishing them under a Creative Commons CC licence, which allows for the reuse of that data. Yet, a key value of sharing one's research data in this way is to diversify the range of data available (not only to GPTs but to other academics and students) and, as such, to create new training materials for a more ethically sophisticated AI that has better access to data from parts of the world poorly represented in global data. If we imagine datasets of all the primary materials discussed and referred to by, for example, an Africanist scholar over the course of their career, or even those materials referred to in any given publication, in which data on how to access those primary materials is also captured, one starts to get a sense of what this kind of practice might enable.

Publishing such data can also demythologise the process of knowledge production, from the research phase to data creation or collection, to analysis and to eventual publication. Instead of the final product being the singularly valued object of knowledge production, we can build infrastructure for other scholars to deepen or broaden analysis on a greater range of works. This challenges the non-communal and extractive model of the singular researcher, the approach that dominates the field in which singular analysis is taken *as knowledge production*. Publishing open access data or research notes, on the other hand, or finding ways of working together to address the larger issues of data inequality and colonial ontologies requires us to set a new standard for how we value academic work. It requires communities with a wide range of expertise and a shared commitment to address the problem of a tightening circle of colonial knowledge. This is not work that can be done by individuals or within one field alone: we need robust collaborations across the fields of literary studies, library and information science, digital humanities, and multi-language linguistics. We need new models of assessing research outputs that value a knowledge production that ensures the future of the field, rather one that attenuates it.

Conclusion

What this paper has tried to establish is the entanglement between the methods and praxis that dominates our field of African literature and AI to better understand how that relationship may threaten or enable the propagation of this field. It is not any single factor in our production process of knowledge in the field of African literature that is singularly the problem. There is, however, a tangible threat to the field that comes from the hand-in-glove relationships between a certain type of knowledge production (single-authored publications

– often via the method of close readings) and a certain type of career-building that depends on precisely that kind of production. Combined with the corporatization of academic publishing and of the data that has been produced wholesale for consumption by bots crawling the web for content to feed LLMs, these factors point towards a massive thinning out of the visible and usable primary and secondary materials on African literatures being used, at scale, in the field.

To do the work of decolonization in the face of these cannibalistic and extractive tendencies of AI is to introduce new methods in all aspects of our literary practice, from the skills we teach students, to how we share our research results and data, to how we cooperate with colleagues to create better, multilingual, and diverse data. Some of these methods require us to practice skills that Rachel Sagner Buurma and Jon Shaw's idea of slow metadata capture: accuracy, care, and methodical collection, annotation and structuring of data. Other methods include collaborative work and an openness to sharing research data as part of the research commons. What is more challenging is the work we need to do as collectives to unpick the ontologies that underscore how our field is organised (in the variety of institutions it traverses). This is no small feat: it requires a level of coordination and collaboration that the very structures of our university systems resist.

Whether we can, even slightly, steer the course of where multinational corporate AI is heading remains to be seen, but at least building an awareness of these matters of scale into our research and teaching practice can be transformative to pull back on the massive overproduction of knowledge on only a very few texts that currently dominates our field.

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